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EXAMINING THE PHYSICAL TO VISUAL SHIFT IN HOW WE NOW EXPERIENCE DESIGNED OBJECTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper chronicles an investigation involving a group of design students from Northumbria University, School of Design. The investigation presented the opportunity to validate a framework that correlates the physical access of designed objects against the visual attention these objects gained through media including exhibitions. The outcome of this case study aims to better understand how the shift from physically to visually consumed designed objects impacts on industrial design students. Specifically the way they access and use design material for inspiration, learn about design and develop their ambitions to work as designers.

Keywords: Physical, Visual, Consumption.

INTRODUCTION

Historically, industrial design has been viewed by the industry and society as a combination of applied art and science brought together to develop products that work on several levels including aesthetic, ergonomic, functional, producible, and marketable. The role of an industrial designer, therefore, is to design and create solutions that maximize the potential utility and commercial success of the product through consideration of its form, usability, marketing, manufacture, and sales amongst other elements (Potter, 2002). From tables to cars, vacuum cleaners to telephones and lamps to lighters, industrial design, in a conventional sense, is concerned with enriching people's lives whilst at the same time designing more functionally robust products, less expensive services, and systems that

reduce damage to the environment (Rodgers, 2009). In most cases, the day-to-day work of industrial design results in the production of physical goods that remain largely outside the world of the media (Munari, 1971). By this we mean that the majority of goods produced and used widely are highly tangible. They are real, touchable, physical objects but their visibility on the increasingly intrusive and ubiquitous world of the media such as magazines, websites and exhibition events is close to zero.

In recent years, however, there has been an increasing shift in the power and reach of the media within a design context (McRobbie, 1998). This is particularly evident in relation to the design and production of limited edition and one-off design pieces. We have witnessed a growing phenomenon in the number of these objects being produced, which have quickly become part of private and public collections. Typically, these goods are traded through auctions, which results in them being inaccessible as usable objects for the primary function they are supposed to perform. For example, Tejo Remy's "You Can't Lay Down Your Memory" Chest of Drawers (1991), made from conventional materials such as maple, metal, plastic, burlap and oak, was produced in a limited series of 200 and has been the subject of auction sales all over the world. It is highly unlikely that this particular product will be considered by the broader audience as a chest of drawers where to actually store clothing given that there are only 200 of them in existence and their auction price is in the region of 30,000 US Dollars per piece.

Figure 2. "You Can't Lay Down Your memory" Chest of Drawers, Tejo Remy. 1991. Metal, paper, plastic, burlap, contact paper and paint, 55 1/2 x 53 x 20" (141 x 134.6 x 50.8 cm)

Similarly, the 10 Lockheed Lounge chairs (1986) designed by Marc Newson have all been sold to collectors and museums through auction houses. In 2009, Phillips de Pury & Company in London sold one of Newson's Lockheed Lounge chairs for £1,105,250 setting a record for the highest price paid in history for furniture by a living designer (Phillips de Pury & C., 2009). Although very few people have had the opportunity of experiencing that object as a chair, meaning actually sitting on it, its representation has reached a very broad audience via magazines, websites, videos and exhibitions. The use of the chair in a popular music video by Madonna allowed its visual representation to extend considerably its audience beyond the circle of design practitioners, educators, students and connoisseurs. While the Lockheed Lounge chair remains a very exclusive object, its representation is consumed globally, broadly distributed whilst consumed only on a visual level (du Gay, 1997).

Motivated by Sam Hecht's lecture during the debate held on Tuesday 21st September 2010 at the Royal Society for the encouragement of Arts, Manufactures & Commerce, in which he stated that "A lot of design is consumed as images rather than as a physicality." (Hecht, 2010). We wanted to understand how students are influenced in their inspiration to study design and motivation of

Figure 1. "Lockheed Lounge" Chair, Marc Newson. 1988. Fibreglass-reinforced polyester resin core, blind-riveted sheet aluminium, paint, 34 1/2 x 65 3/4 x 24 1/2 in. (87.6 x 167 x 62.2 cm).

pursuing their design careers by the visual consumption compared to the physical consumption of selected objects and how these are perceived differently (Mackay, 1997).

Physical consumption is meant in this paper as the tangible experience of the object happening through its use. The visual consumption, instead, is determined by the experience that one can have through solely sense of sight.

METHODOLOGY

Starting from a previously developed framework (figure 3) that puts into correlation the physical accessibility with the media attention of objects, this investigation has involved, 17 undergraduate students of the Northumbria University in Newcastle upon Tyne. The group was composed of 9 students from the 3D design course and 8 from the Design for the Industry course who were asked to undertake an anonymous questionnaire. The focus of both courses is mainly product design.

This group has engaged students in their second, third and fourth year of study. First year students have been excluded as we wanted to consider only students who had already been exposed and educated in design and are in the process of building their design knowledge and ambitions.

We believe that the results of these 17 are representative of the thoughts of Northumbria University students.

Intentionally, students were not made aware of the framework we developed. Colour images of the objects and corresponding questions were included

in the questionnaire printed on single sheets, so that students could go through the questionnaire following the order they preferred.

Some of the questions adopted a Likert scale system with scores from 1 to 5 (Babbie, 1992).

Students were asked to answer as candidly as possible and not to think of the questionnaire as an evaluating tool for judging their knowledge and their conception of design. In this sense anonymity was necessary in letting students go freely through the questions.

Questions had the double purpose of verifying that objects were correctly placed in the framework according to students' encounters and experience of the items (i) and understand what role selected objects had played in influencing students' inspiration to study design, learn about design and motivation to pursue a design career (ii). Results were then collected, analyzed, visualized and interpreted as reported in the following sections.

MEDIA ATTENTION VS PHYSICAL ACCESSIBILITY FRAMEWORK

This investigation is part of a larger research project that is currently in progress. The research examines the transformation of our focus on actual, physical designed artefacts to one where our attention has shifted to the representation of these designed objects, and the way they are mediated and consumed. The increasing visibility of these designed artefacts in our media-driven modern culture have at the same time led to the abandonment and loss of the designed artefacts' function of use (Hecht, 2010). That is, the main function now appears to be the representation of such goods and the media profile of their creators (Long, 2006). The industry that has flourished around the representation of design has played an important role in increasing the presence of design artefacts in printed and new media, Internet websites, and the exhibitions of design objects during design festivals and events (van Kersten, 2010).

For better clarity we developed a visual framework reflecting on design (figure 3), illustrating the relationship between the physical accessibility of selected designed objects on the horizontal axis, with their visibility in media including exhibitions on the vertical axis. Physical accessibility is mainly

determined by the number of copies in circulation and in actual use by people, contexts for 'physical access' and experience are people's homes and shops where in fact a tangible experience of use of the object is allowed. On the contrary, 'media attention' is represented by the presence of certain artefacts as the subject of a communication through media. Exhibitions are also included in what we conventionally define as media (i.e. magazines, books, the internet, etc.). In fact, similarly to media, exhibitions are contexts for a visual consumption as the tangible experience of the displayed objects is denied by a set of rules, moreover conventional elements of the surrounding, such as plinths and spotlights, concoct a focus on the visual representation of the object (Staniszewski, 1998).

FRAMEWORK DETAIL

For the purpose of this investigation we have selected three representative objects for each of the four quadrants. Thus, in the top-left quadrant (I) we see designed objects produced in very small numbers (Ron Arad's Rover Chair, 1981; Marc Newson's Lockheed Lounge Chair, 1986; Tejo Remy's "You can't Lay Down Your Memory" chest of drawers, 1991) but represented in substantial numbers across the media. Conversely, in the bottom-right quadrant (III) we find a range of objects that are manufactured in their millions (Yale Padlock, 1948; GEM Paperclip, 1899; wooden pencil with eraser, 1858) but remain outside the focus of media attention. In the top-right quadrant (II) we include objects that reached both a great visibility on media and have been sold in considerable numbers (Earl Dean's Coca Cola bottle, 1915; Philippe Starck's Juicy Salif squeezer, 1988; Richard Sapper's Tizio lamp, 1971). The bottom-left quadrant (IV) features objects designed by students, that remain at the stage of unique pieces and that also have never received considerable media attention (Kwak Chul An's Materializing Dematerialization, 2010; Tomm Velthuis' Treintafel 2009; Hans Tan's Bamboo Chaise, 2005).

All the objects selected have received high appreciation from the context that generated them and beyond it. In fact objects of the first, second and third quadrant have been acquired through the

time by prestigious public and private collections, while objects of the fourth quadrant are school projects by successful students of the Design Academy Eindhoven. We selected items that generally hold a certain appeal for designers because of their qualities and impact on society or design community (Fukasawa and Morrison, 2006).

TESTING THE FRAMEWORK WITH STUDENTS

The framework from which this research derived, is conceived only on a theoretical level. For this investigation we needed to verify if it applied to the students, thus meaning if really our assumptions about the physical accessibility and media attention of the objects of the four quadrants would have been confirmed by our students. For this purpose we asked them about each object if they could recognize it, if they had used it and where they had seen it. Results are visualized as in Figure 4.

As expected students typically recognize objects of the first, second and third quadrant (in green colour in fig. 4), while objects of the fourth quadrant are mostly unknown to the students (red colour). Results also confirmed the accessibility of use to objects of

the third quadrant, which in fact have been used by most students (in white colour). While objects on the first quadrant have clearly been experienced visually rather than by physical use. However two students claimed they have used the Rover chair designed by Ron Arad and one claims to have sat on the Lockheed Lounge by Newson. In the first case it is possible that the students intended the Rover Chair as the actual seat of the British car or maybe they were lucky enough to really sit on the Rover Chair or Lockheed Lounge at some events. We doubt that this is possible, considering that is widely accepted that rare pieces aren't to be touched. One student declared not to recognize the Coca Cola bottle, while all the students have used it. This is an anomalous result which happened to appear in the questionnaires run with students either because of their misunderstanding of the question or simply choosing the wrong box when filling the form. However, these few anomalies don't seem to compromise the general plausibility of the framework and questionnaire.

To better understand where students encounter selected objects we provided them with a list of

Figure 3. Designed Objects Copies in Circulation set against Media Attention.

contexts for each object so that they could choose where they had seen the items.

The options included:

- Somebody's house
- Shop
- Book
- Web
- Magazine
- Exhibition

Students could choose more than one option.

Results confirmed expectations of the framework by showing how objects of the first quadrant (top-left) are accessible visually in context such as Books, Web, Magazines and Exhibitions.

Objects of the second quadrant (top-right) have been encountered by students both in contexts where it is

possible to better experience their physical features, such as somebody's house and shops, as well as contexts where interaction is mainly visual, like media including exhibitions. The Tizio Lamp by Sapper constitutes an exception as according to students it doesn't have a high physical accessibility or media attention. However this result can be explained in the limited exposure of the students to this specific object which - we believe - still fits in the second quadrant, maybe just positioned in its lower-left corner.

The third quadrant (bottom-right) is characterized by objects that have been largely encountered in domestic contexts as well as shops. Some students also declared they had seen these objects in the media as well.

Objects of the fourth quadrant (bottom-left) receive very low scores as almost none of the students have seen those before. This was expected due to the peculiarly scarce media attention and physical

Figure 4. Visualized answers from students to the questions: "Do you recognize this object?", "Have you ever used it?", "Where have you seen it?"

accessibility of objects belonging to this quadrant. Generally, the framework was validated by students' answers. However, what we wanted to achieve was to observe the influence that visual and physical consumption of design material has on students in their path in design.

PHYSICALLY AND VISUALLY CONSUMED OBJECTS IN THE PATH OF A DESIGNER - RESULTS

The career of a design student of our time can be defined in 3 key moments: deciding whether to enrol at an undergraduate design school (i), studying and learning what design is according to the educators in University (ii), developing motivation to work as a designer (iii).

Our questionnaire looked at these three key passages in relation to the physical and visual consumption of designed objects.

WHAT BRINGS STUDENTS TO STUDY DESIGN AT UNIVERSITY

One of the questions we asked to students read: *"On a scale from 1 to 5, how much did this object inspire you to study design?"* Where 1 stood for no inspiration and 5 for great inspiration. Then we calculated the mean score that each object registered, by summing all the scores from 1 to 5 and dividing by the number of the participating students. Clearly we wanted to understand which objects, among the ones selected, played a role in driving future design students' attention towards design. At the top three places in this particular ranking we found:

1. Lockheed Chair by Newson (mean score 2.7)
2. Coca Cola bottle by Dean (mean score 2.5)
3. Juicy Salif by Starck (mean score 2.3)

The nine remaining objects followed the top three with scores ranging from 2.1 and 1.5. As expected, objects of the fourth quadrant occupied the lowest positions since students couldn't be aware of those when deciding to enrol in Northumbria University. Notably, the three most inspiring objects to study design belong to the first and second quadrant, the ones denoting a high media attention.

WHAT DESIGN STUDENTS LEARN TO BE GOOD DESIGN

Another question asked for each object was *"On a scale from 1 to 5, how good is the design?"*, where 1 was meant as bad design and 5 represented great design. We believe that students' answers were in large scale influenced by what they learn in school through lessons and assignments. Students indicated as best design the one of:

1. GEM Paperclip (mean score 4.1)
2. YALE Padlock (mean score 4.0)
3. Wooden pencil with eraser (mean score 3.9)

These three objects definitely out rated the other nine. Remarkably the top 3 objects belong to the third quadrant which contains objects of high accessibility and low visibility on media.

Objects that played important roles as inspirational material ranked lower in the chart, with Philippe Starck's Juicy Salif and Marc Newson's Lockheed positioned in the lower half.

We believe these results partially reflect the knowledge and values that undergraduate students absorb while studying and practicing design at the Northumbria University.

WHAT MOTIVATES STUDENTS TO WORK AS DESIGNERS

Another question we included was *"On a scale from 1 to 5, how much does this object motivates you to pursue your career as a designer?"*, 1 representing no motivation, while 5 standing for great motivation. Student's preferences resulted in the following ranking:

1. Coca Cola bottle by Dean (mean score 2.7)
2. Lockheed Chair by Newson (mean score 2.5)
3. Juicy Salif by Starck (mean score 2.5)

The resulting chart closely resembles the one of the inspiration to study design, although slightly re-arranged in some positions. Objects that served as strong inspiration to study design, are also the ones that motivate students to work as design professionals. Leading positions are held by the Coca Cola bottle, Stark's juicer and Newson's Lounge. There are no particularly relevant changes in the position following the first three, except for the

Figure 5. Graph visualizing students' different consideration of selected objects before studies, while studying and after studies

Rover Chair by Arad that falls into the last place. However we do not have enough elements to justify this result as we couldn't follow with interviews due to the anonymity of the questionnaire.

PHYSICAL VS. VISUAL IN THE PRE-STUDY, STUDY AND PRACTICE STAGES

The three results reported in previous paragraphs are representative for the development of a young designer.

Figure 5 shows the three resulting charts of inspiration to study design, good design and motivation to study design on a timescale for a clearer visualization of the information gathered. Figure 6 substitutes each object with the visualized data deriving from students' answers to the question "Have you ever used it?". Thus allowing us to notice how students' physical experience of use, plays a crucial role in determining the 'goodness' of the design. In fact, those objects that students have used are the same ones that rank higher in the chart for the quality of the design.

Similar conclusions cannot be made about the inspiration and the motivation that the same objects provide for students. Here the physical use is not as influential in determining their impact on design students.

Figure 6. Graph visualizing students' different consideration of selected objects before studies, while studying and after studies in relation to their use

Figure 7, most notably, shows how the three objects that students declare of being of most inspiration to study design and motivation to work as a designer, correspond to the three with the highest attention from media, intended as the sum of students' sightings of the objects on books, web, magazines and exhibitions. These objects are: the Coca Cola bottle, the Juicy Salif squeezer and the Lockheed Lounger which score respectively 17, 36 and 32 sightings on media. The Rover Chair constitutes the only exception to this trend, as it registers only one more point in students' spotting on media than the Coca Cola Bottle, but ranks lower in the charts.

Figure 7. Top three objects in inspiring to study design and motivating to pursue a design career

Figure 8. Summarize of students' consideration of objects with high media attention opposed to the ones with high physical accessibility through the three key stages of pre-study, study and practice.

The presence of these three objects at the top of inspiration and motivation charts, is indicative of how visually consumed objects play an important role in pushing design to study and then work as designers.

Figure 8 is a synthesis of the path of Northumbria students. Here it is highlighted how objects receiving high media attention are given of greater importance in pushing students to study design and then pursue their career as designers. Conversely, utilitarian objects, easily accessible on a physical level, are the ones with the highest consideration while studying, but with little appeal in motivating students to enrol in a design school or work as designers.

The discrepancy between what students learn being good design and what instead motivates them intrigued us, so we decided to investigate further on this aspect.

MOTIVATING DESIGN VS GOOD DESIGN

As design educators, we would like to see our students being motivated by what they learn to regard as good design. The better the design, the more motivating it should be for pursuing a career in design. In reality such a trend is not to be found among undergraduate students of Northumbria University in the sample here.

In figure 9, objects are placed in a graph according to the 'goodness' of their design on a vertical axis set against the motivation the items provide to students on the horizontal axis. It appears even more evident the disconnection between good and motivating design already highlighted in previous sections of this paper.

Figure 9. Graph visualizing the relation between "Good" and "Motivating" design.

It is worth noticing once more how well a piece like the Juicy Salif is able to perform in terms of motivation, especially when the quality of its design is so poorly appraised by students.

We were particularly interested in better understanding what qualities of the objects students would appreciate the most in expressing their preferences for what they think is good design and what instead motivates them to work as designers. For this purpose, we included one question in the form that would have provided information on that. In fact for each object we asked students "It features a good...", the options were:

- Aesthetics
- Functionality
- Use of materials
- Sustainability
- Cultural relevance

Students could select as many qualities as they liked. Students' choices resulted in the graph in figure 10, which shows students' high appreciation for the

aesthetics of objects with high media attention, like the Starck's squeezer (15 students marked a preference for its aesthetics), the Coca Cola bottle (14 preferences) and the Newson's Lounger (8 preferences). While objects like the paperclip, the pencil and the padlock are regarded by students for their functionality, receiving preference from respectively 17, 16 and 15 students for that particular aspect.

Figure 10. Graph showing which qualities students appreciate in each object.

Generally speaking, the most evident results see objects in the second quadrant, standing out for their aesthetic qualities, while objects of the third quadrant feature an evident functionality with all 17 students declaring the good functionality of a paperclip. Visualized data about objects' peculiarities were then inserted in the graph visualizing the relation between good and motivating design, as it is visible in figure 11. In this visualization it is possible to notice how the most motivating objects (towards the right of the graph) feature higher aesthetic qualities, while objects of good design (towards the upper part of the graph) feature best functionality.

As to say that for Northumbria design students functionality determines what is good design, while aesthetics acts as a strong driving force in providing motivation.

This confirms how physical access is crucial for students in determining what is good design, while a visual interaction, which is how students usually

Figure 11. Objects as their qualities in the graph visualizing the relation between motivation and good design.

experience aesthetics, is enough for influencing inspiration and motivation.

A quality like the one of aesthetics, being mainly visual, can be supported by media (Coles, 2007), thus justifying how objects like the Juicy Salif or the Lockheed Lounge, which have been used by very few students can still have a big influence on students' motivation to become design professionals. Similarly the quality of functionality, which is better supported by the physical experience of use and which determines students' perception of what is good design, has to be found in objects that populate people's everyday life in the *real world*. (Papanek, 1985).

The high appreciation for the Coca Cola bottle as a motivating object and partially also as one of good design is explainable by its good aesthetics and good functionality. In fact the Coca Cola bottle is recognized by students as an object that features high media attention, but also high physical accessibility.

CONCLUSIONS

Our aim in this investigation was to explore whether the shift from physically consumed to visually consumed designed objects has had a significant impact on industrial design students. Particularly, regarding the manner in which the students consume and use design material, develop ambitions and ultimately conceive of design and its practice. We witness the inspirational and motivational impact of visual consumption of objects with a higher media presence, including exhibitions, in the students' decisions to study and work in design. In these contexts students find the best aesthetics. The tangible realm of utilitarian objects is recognized by students as one of good design, where function of use is highly appreciated. However, the results show that objects of this context don't appeal students as much as the ones in realm of media and exhibitions. In those realms, aesthetics are optimally supported and provide the underlying motivation for students to become practitioners of design. This investigation is better termed a case study which constitutes a part a wider process of research and further study. Extending from Hecht's statement that "most of the students designed with the media in mind" (Hecht, 2010), we can firmly conclude that design consumed on media and exhibitions is, for students of this sample, not only influential to develop their motivation in pursuing a design career, but also provides the momentum for students to study design at University.

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